

Gender STI

D.4.1 – Action plan for policy recommendations on gender equality in STI dialogues

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This action plan outlines a comprehensive strategy aimed at enhancing the integration of gender equality in Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) collaborations. Aligned with the findings of the previous activities of the Gender STI Project, in particular the outputs and insights gathered through Co-design Labs and expert opinion workshops, the action plan presents a set of recommendations to foster gender equality within formal bilateral and multilateral agreements, STI implementation activities, and the dissemination of international STI dialogues and cooperation efforts. The plan emphasizes collaborative development and acknowledges the diverse cultural and institutional contexts across EU Member States (MS), Associated Countries (AC), and third countries on three levels:

- **Formal Agreements in STI International Cooperation:** To strengthen gender equality, this plan advocates for the inclusion of explicit gender-responsive provisions within formal bilateral and multilateral STI agreements between MS, AC, and the identified third countries. These provisions will emphasize the integration of gender perspectives into project design, decision-making processes, and allocation of resources. By incorporating gender considerations at the foundational level of agreements, we can ensure that gender equality becomes an inherent principle in all collaborative STI endeavors.
- **Gender Integration in STI Implementation:** The plan recommends proactive measures to ensure gender equality in STI implementation activities. This involves designing grant access procedures that promote inclusivity, setting gender-balanced participation requirements, and implementing a comprehensive evaluation process that assesses the impact of gender equality measures. By eliminating barriers and fostering an environment of equitable participation, we can harness the full potential of diverse talents and perspectives in advancing STI initiatives.
- **Dissemination and Promotion of Gender-Inclusive STI Cooperation:** The plan highlights the need for targeted efforts in the dissemination and promotion of STI international dialogues and cooperation. It suggests the development of gender-responsive evaluation frameworks and roadmaps that track progress and identify areas for improvement in gender equality within STI collaborations. By sharing best practices, success stories, and challenges openly, we can facilitate cross-learning and inspire a culture of continuous improvement in the integration of the gender perspective in STI dialogues.

In conclusion, this action plan provides a roadmap to elevate gender equality within STI collaborations across three key levels. By embedding gender considerations into STI agreements, implementation activities, and dissemination efforts, we can catalyze the transformative change that leverages the power of inclusivity and diversity. Through collaborative implementation, we commit to forging a future where gender equality is a cornerstone of STI partnerships, leading to more innovative, sustainable, and impactful outcomes for all stakeholders involved. The plan will serve as a common foundation for collective efforts to transform recommendations into actionable measures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Gender STI project, funded by the European Union, is a pioneering initiative focused on advancing gender equality within the realm of Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI). This project is dedicated to addressing systemic gender disparities that persist within research, innovation, and technological development across Europe and third countries.

The project's primary objective is to promote a paradigm shift in the STI landscape by integrating gender perspectives into all aspects of the research and innovation cycle. Through an interdisciplinary approach, it seeks to empower individuals of all genders, eliminate gender biases, and drive equitable participation and representation. The project focuses on three main challenges pursued by the EU strategy for gender equality in R&I:

Figure 1: Challenges of the Gender STI project

In this context, the Gender STI action plan has been developed, which encompasses the recommendations derived from the exploration of the three defined challenges in the project activities: mapping of bilateral and multilateral agreements, surveys and interviews regarding gender equality implementation, benchmarking in STI dialogues, Co-Design Labs and workshops with experts on gender equality and international dialogues in STI.

These recommendations underwent a reflective exercise regarding their potential implementation and impact based on specific criteria (see Annex A). Subsequently, a workshop was conducted, involving 22 experts from around the world, to establish prioritization and refine recommendations where necessary (see Annex B). Following this comprehensive process, a total of 17 recommendations were distilled, which form the core of the action plan. Each recommendation is accompanied by concrete actions for implementation, stakeholders required to be involved, and a proposed timeline.

The Gender STI project envisions a future where inclusiveness is seamlessly woven into the fabric of scientific discovery, technological innovation, and research collaborations. The proposed recommendations will contribute to dismantle barriers, promote inclusive practices, and harness the full potential of diverse talents, and thus to a more just, equitable, and prosperous society where STI advancements benefit everyone.

Through the collaborative efforts of stakeholders, researchers, innovators, policymakers, and visionary individuals and organizations that advocate for gender equality in R&I, Gender STI seeks to create a lasting legacy of gender-inclusive STI practices that pave the way for a more progressive and sustainable future.

2 METHODOLOGY TO FORMULATE RECOMMENDATIONS

2.1 A preliminary set of recommendations

The first step undertaken within the framework of the action plan consisted of a comprehensive exploration of the insights derived from the Design Thinking process used in the Gender STI project. This intricate process aimed to extract valuable perspectives and innovative ideas, which were subsequently utilized in crafting a series of strategic recommendations and policy actions. The overarching objective of these recommendations and actions was to catalyze a substantial enhancement in the integration of gender equality across a wide spectrum of bilateral and multilateral initiatives involving European Union Member States, Associated Countries, and third countries within the realm of Science, Technology, and Innovation.

The resulting recommendations and policy actions were meticulously defined within the three challenges of the project: gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions, and integration of the gender dimension research and innovation content. This encompassed fostering gender parity, equitable participation, and unbiased representation within diverse STI undertakings spanning EU MS, AC, and third countries.

In essence, this preliminary stage of the action plan underscored the significance of drawing upon the rich insights garnered from the Gender STI project's Design Thinking methodology. By channeling these insights into well-crafted recommendations and policy actions, the aim was to instigate a transformative shift that not only acknowledges gender equality's vital role but actively incorporates it into the core fabric of bilateral and multilateral STI initiatives across borders.

Among the previous activities undertaken within the project, which served as foundational sources for deriving the subsequent recommendations, the following standout:

- **Mapping and Analysis of Gender Equality in STI Agreements:** A comprehensive mapping exercise was conducted in WP1 (528 agreements were revised), delving into the intricacies of gender equality within bilateral and multilateral agreements in the realm of Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI). The insights garnered from this mapping exercise provided a solid groundwork for shaping informed recommendations.
- **Gender Equality Implementation Survey in STI Agreements:** WP1 survey (204 responses) was administered to find out to what extent gender equality considerations are effectively implemented within STI bilateral and multilateral agreements. The survey results contributed vital insights to the formulation of recommendations aimed at enhancing gender equality integration.
- **Comparative Analysis and Benchmarking on Gender Equality in STI Dialogues:** A rigorous comparative analysis (based on 80 in deep interviews with stakeholders) was undertaken in WP2, benchmarking the gender equality landscape across various STI dialogues. By scrutinizing and comparing gender-related approaches, practices, and outcomes, this analysis provided a nuanced understanding of disparities and best practices. Such insights served as a

cornerstone in crafting recommendations to bridge gender equality gaps in STI dialogues.

- **Discussion and Prototypes from Co-Design Labs:** Three Co-Design Labs were carried out during the project and facilitated collaborative discussions and idea generation, resulting in innovative prototypes and concepts. These Labs acted as a crucible for brainstorming gender-inclusive approaches, mechanisms, and strategies to address challenges within STI collaborations. Eighteen prototypes emerged from these labs offering concrete starting points for actionable recommendations.

Collectively, these activities provided a multifaceted perspective on the gender equality landscape within STI agreements and dialogues. The insights gleaned from the mapping, survey, analysis, and co-design labs were harnessed to formulate robust recommendations that align with the overarching objective of fostering gender equality across bilateral and multilateral STI engagements.

The formulation of recommendations was led by UPM, while all project partners contributed their expertise. This approach ensured that the recommendations were not only informed by a wide array of perspectives but also embraced the full spectrum of expertise held by the project partners. The resulting set of recommendations represents a culmination of intellectual rigor, multidisciplinary insights, and collaborative effort, setting the stage for impactful and effective strategies to enhance gender equality within STI dialogues and agreements.

2.2 Criteria for selecting the recommendations

In order to facilitate the process of prioritizing the recommendations, a set of criteria was established to assess both implementation feasibility and potential impact. This assessment considered the diverse cultural perspectives and varying manifestations of gender equality within the Science, Technology, and Innovation context across the European Union, Member States, Associated Countries, and the 10 selected third-country partners.

As an initial step, a comprehensive criteria table was meticulously crafted to provide guidance during the creative ideation phase of prototypes within the co-design labs of WP3. These criteria were thoughtfully divided into two categories: general criteria, which addressed overarching considerations, and cross-cutting criteria, which took into consideration the multifaceted and interrelated nature of gender equality in STI. Each criterion in the table was accompanied by a descriptive explanation, allowing for a clear understanding of its relevance and implications. The overarching purpose of this criteria table was to offer a structured framework for evaluating the priority level of each criterion. This evaluation was conducted on a scale of low, medium, high, or deemed irrelevant, with respect to each of the three primary project topics, referred to as "challenges."

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
CRITERIA	DESCRIPTION	TOPIC			STAKEHOLDERS	COMMENTS	HOW TO READ TABLE	
		GE CAREERS	GENDER BALANCE DECISION-MAKING	GENDER DIMENSION R&I CONTENT				
3	Acceptability	Effort/benefit balance for risk mitigation of rejection of the action					Each proposed criteria has a description attached to it. Under "topic" each cell has a drop-down list which allows priority selection for each criteria in regards to elements of weighting. Under "Stakeholders" please add the name of your organisation and the category (Ministry, RPD, University, NGO...)	
4	Accountability	Actions can be assigned to persons/bodies						
5	Adaptability	Can be adapted according to country-specific legislation or cultural differences without jeopardizing the key objectives						
6	Cost/Benefit	Costs should be reasonable with respect to benefits						
7	Implementation Timeline	The recommendation should be able to be implemented/started in the short term (less than 3 years)						
8	Measurability	Actions can be evaluated with both qualitative and quantitative indicators						
9	Repeatability	Action can be duplicated for different countries and stakeholders						
10	Snowball Effect	Snowball effect: can 1 recommendation about group A have a further impact on group B (because group A, e.g. board members and top executives, has an effect on group B, e.g. academic staff)						
11	Social Impact	On societal issues (health, environment, AI...), women empowerment, job creation						
12	Sustainability	Actions and impacts go beyond the agreement framework and timeline and are able to be maintained				Longevity		
13	Tried and True	Action has already been successfully implemented in one country or domain/in line with existing policies				R/a. Robustness		
14			Transversal Criteria					
15	Cultural Specificity	Do not reject or downgrade systematically the recommendations which are specific to certain cultures or countries (do not always prioritize recommendations implementable in all countries of the consortium) -> keep in mind to select some country/culture specific recommendations				because of the discrepancies between countries and the legal differences, some recommendations may be impossible to implement or on the contrary are already existing. As long as a recommendation may improve the situation in some countries, especially if they are least advanced in terms of equality policies, they should be taken into consideration		
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Figure 2: First criteria table

The criteria that supported the selection of recommendations for the Action Plan are the following:

- **Acceptability:** Effort/benefit balance for risk mitigation of rejection of the action.
- **Accountability:** Actions can be assigned to persons/bodies.
- **Adaptability:** Can be adapted according to country-specific legislation or cultural differences without jeopardizing the key objectives.
- **Cost/Benefit:** Costs should be reasonable with respect to benefits.
- **Implementation Timeline:** The recommendation should be able to be implemented/started in the short term (less than 3 years).
- **Measurability:** Actions can be evaluated with both qualitative and quantitative indicators.
- **Repeatability:** Actions can be duplicated for different countries and stakeholders.
- **Snowball Effect:** Can the recommendation about group A have a further impact on group B? (because group A, e.g. board members and top executives, has an effect on group B, e.g. academic staff).
- **Social Impact:** On societal issues (health, environment, AI...), women empowerment, job creation, etc.
- **Sustainability:** Actions and impacts go beyond the agreement framework and timeline and are able to be maintained.
- **Tried and True:** Action has already been successfully implemented in one country or domain/in line with existing policies.
- **Cultural Specificity:** Do not reject or downgrade systematically the recommendations which are specific to certain cultures or countries (do not always prioritize recommendations implementable in all countries of the consortium) keep in mind to select some country/culture specific recommendations. Because of the

discrepancies between countries and the legal differences, some recommendations may be impossible to implement or on the contrary are already existing. As long as a recommendation may improve the situation in some countries, especially if they are least advanced in terms of equality policies, they should be taken into consideration.

By integrating this systematic approach, the project aimed to ensure a well-informed and comprehensive assessment of the recommendations' potential, considering various dimensions of their implementation and the varying degrees of impact they might have across the complex landscape of gender equality within STI collaborations.

As we transitioned to the practical phase of assessing the formulated recommendations against the established criteria, a decision was made to streamline the process for enhanced efficiency. To achieve this, a more straightforward approach was adopted: a new table was created where each recommendation only needed to be marked as either meeting or not meeting the criteria. The outcome with the preliminary list of recommendations matched with the criteria can be found in annex A.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
2	N	From	Challenge	Recommendation	Acceptability	Accountability	Adaptability	Cost/Benefit	Timeline	Measurability	Repeatability	Snowball effect	Social impact	Sustainability	Tried and true	Cultural specificity	
3	1	WP2 interviews, LAB1 Prototype 2.1, LAB2 Prototype 2.1	CH1, CH2	Sex-disaggregated data should be included in the monitoring and evaluation of international research programmes (e.g. application and success rate for women and men applicants, research team's composition, share of women with a senior role/team leader, share of women with permanent contract, leave policies, composition of evaluation panels and other decision-making bodies)	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	☐	☒	☒	☒	
4	2	WP2 interviews, LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH1, CH2, CH3	Negotiating and including clear gender equality clauses in international agreements, in alignment with the Lubiana Declaration or other international manifestos, with three main objectives: gender equality in careers (e.g. obligation to develop incentive campaigns at the undergraduate level to encourage women to develop and lead STI projects), gender balance in decision-making, gender dimension in research content.	☒	☒	☐	☐	☐	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	☒	
5	3	LAB1 Prototype 2.1, LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH1	Include in international agreements the organization of a Women in STI research day/symposium at research organizations where role models can be highlighted, women scientists can present their research and network with other women researchers to identify opportunities for future collaboration	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	
6	4	WP2 interviews	CH1, CH2, CH3	STI dialogues should require the implementation of a Gender Equality Plan, with measure goals in the short and long term, which allow strategies to be adjusted	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	☒	
7	5	WP2 interviews	CH1	Promoting gender sensitive fundings to promote the participation of women in science in international scientific cooperation	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	
8	6	WP2 interviews	CH1	STI dialogues and international cooperation actions should set quantified targets to increase the number of female scientists	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	☒	☒	☐	☒	☒	☐	☒	
9	7	WP2 interviews	CH1, CH3	Ministries and research performing organizations should communicate and disseminate in the media the activities carried out in STI projects and highlight the participation of women as well as the impact of the research projects that have integrated a sex/gender/intersectional dimension	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	
10	8	LAB2 Prototype 2.1	CH1	International agreements should raise awareness on gender equality in international conferences committees, publications.	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	☐	☒	☐	☒	☒	☐	☒	
11	9	LAB2 Prototype 2.1	CH2	Networks of women in science diplomacy should be invited and involved in governance bodies (steering committees, executive committees...) of the international scientific agreements and policy dialogues. The development of women's networks should be encouraged.	☐	☒	☒	☐	☐	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒	☐	☒	

Figure 3: Recommendations match with criteria

This modification served a dual purpose. Primarily, it functioned as an internal exercise designed to foster reflection and introspection within our team. This process allowed us to consolidate our understanding of the recommendations and their alignment with the criteria, ultimately better preparing us for the subsequent expert workshop. In this forthcoming workshop, our aim was to prioritize the recommendations based on a comprehensive evaluation. The responsibility for completing this exercise fell to the partners actively engaged in the tasks of WP4. Individually, each partner assessed the recommendations against the criteria, leading to a diverse range of perspectives and insights. Subsequently, a collaborative discussion ensued, during which these individual assessments were openly shared and deliberated upon. This collaborative dialogue facilitated the refinement of viewpoints and the eventual achievement of a unanimous consensus on the prioritization of recommendations.

Furthermore, to equip the participating experts with comprehensive context and background information, the list of criteria and their accompanying descriptions were thoughtfully provided as preparatory material. This ensured that the experts engaging in

the recommendation prioritization workshop were well-informed and equipped to contribute meaningfully to the process.

In summary, the adjustment made in the application of criteria streamlined the assessment process and primed our team for a rigorous and well-informed expert workshop. This thoughtful and inclusive approach, bolstered by preparatory materials, exemplified our commitment to a thorough and collaborative prioritization process.

2.3 Workshop on prioritizing recommendations

To ensure a thorough prioritization of recommendations, a collaborative activity took the form of a 2.5-hour online workshop held on June 9th, engaging experts from around the world. The workshop applied the MoSCoW methodology due to its efficacy in the context of a condensed working session. Online meetings were held to align ourselves in the content and organization of the event.

The MoSCoW methodology allowed to validate, prioritise and enrich the recommendations according to four priority that obliged participants to reflect on their importance and relevance. It requires people to place the issues they have identified in the quadrants on the basis of the priority they would give to them.

Figure 4: The MOSCOW prioritization method

The **MoSCoW prioritization method** is a three-step approach to filter and select the issues that emerge during a brainstorming session. MoSCoW stands for **must have, should have, could have, and will not have**.

- M – Must have. This first category includes all the requirements that are necessary for the successful implementation of the specific programme, policy or project.

These should be non-negotiable elements that provide the minimum usable subset (MUST) of requirements.

- S -- Should have. This second category is one step below “must have”. Should-have elements are important for the successful completion and implementation of the programme, policy or project, but they are not necessary. In other words, if should-have requirements are not included in the final recommendations it will still function. However, if should-have elements are included, then they will greatly increase its value. A should-have element can be distinguished from a could-have element by assessing the amount of pain and disruption caused by leaving it out.
- C -- Could have. This category includes issues or requirements that have a much smaller impact when left out of the programme, policy or project. As a result, could-have requirements are often the first ones to be deprioritized -- must-have and should-have requirements will always take precedence. Could-haves can be defined as a desirable element, but an unimportant one. Leaving out this requirement will impact the policy, programme or project less than leaving out a should-have element.
- W – Will not Have. This final category includes all the requirements the team recognizes as not a priority for the project's time frame. Assigning elements to the will-not-have category helps strengthen the focus on requirements in the other three categories, while also setting realistic expectations for what the final product does not include. Furthermore, this category is beneficial in preventing scope creep -- or the tendency for product or project requirements to increase during development beyond what the team anticipated. The team can eventually reprioritize some requirements in the will-not-have group and work them into future projects; others are never used. To differentiate between these types of elements, teams can create subcategories within the will-not-have group to identify which requirements they should still implement and which they can ignore.

For the Gender STI recommendations’ prioritization, we used the first three priority areas of the MOSCOW (Must have, Should have and Can have) and for a question of timing we did not use the fourth one (Will not have).

The MoSCoW method is easy to use and understand. It can help individuals with prioritisation, and provides great benefits to participatory workshops. It is used across a variety of disciplines because it allows everyone involved in a project to know what work needs to be completed first. It can help stakeholders frame discussions about the importance of specific requirements when proposing and defining priorities for recommendations and suggestions or specific actions. Furthermore, prioritising requirements enables stakeholders and participants to understand the amount of effort and resources that will be required for each element and issue.

Besides, a comprehensive participant guide was meticulously crafted. This guide encompassed the agenda, essential preparatory materials (comprising the roster of recommendations and the criteria for contemplating their potential implementation and impact), as well as detailed instructions for the online connection to BERST platform. The tool used during the online work session was groupmap, with a different work canvas for each group.

Agenda for the Workshop		
Time	Title	Presenter
15:00	Welcome	Yolanda Ursa, INMARK
15:05	Presentation the challenges and initial recommendations	Dr. María F. Cabrera, UPM
15:10	Explanation of Moscow methodology	Paolo Martínez, FUTOUR
15:20	Work in groups to reflect on the recommendations	All participants divided in groups
16:20	5 minute break	
16:25	Work in groups to prioritise the recommendations	All participants divided in groups
16:55	Work in groups to think on how to implement the recommendations	All participants divided in groups
17:15	Brief presentation of the work of each group	A representative from each group
17:25	Next steps and farewell	Dr. María F. Cabrera, UPM
17:30	End of the Workshop	

Figure 5: Agenda for the workshop

Invitations were sent to a pool of more than 25 international experts, hailing from beyond the confines of the Gender STI consortium. The final attendance tally stood at 8 esteemed experts, who together with the project participants made up a total of 22 participants of the workshop. Guided by the facilitation expertise of FUTOUR, participants were thoughtfully divided into three distinct working groups, with each group aligned to address a specific challenge. These working groups shouldered the collective responsibility of prioritizing recommendations pertinent to their designated challenge. In cases where refinement was deemed necessary, these groups undertook the task of refining recommendations. Additionally, they proposed concrete actions, identified key stakeholders, and delineated a plausible timeline for the implementation of the identified recommendations.

Figure 6: Participants of the workshop

These working groups shouldered the collective responsibility of prioritizing recommendations pertinent to their designated challenge. In cases where refinement was deemed necessary, these groups undertook the task of refining recommendations. Additionally, they proposed concrete actions, identified key stakeholders, and delineated a plausible timeline for the implementation of the identified recommendations.

The groups adopted the following facilitated process:

- Revise, analyse and reformulate the recommendations when necessary.
- Prioritise them according to the MoSCoW framework.
- Propose actions.

In the first step of the workshop the recommendations for each challenge group were initially described and validated with the experts who had some time comment them and add their suggestions, reflections and ideas.

Figure 7: Example of comments for the validation of a recommendation

In the second step the experts positioned the recommendations in one of the three MoSCoW priority areas. In the figure below, we show how the recommendations addressing the first challenge were prioritised by the participants.

Figure 8: Prioritization of recommendations in the MoSCoW framework

In the third and final step the participants proposed specific actions to foster the implementation of the recommendations that were in the MUST HAVE column. We show below in figure 9 an example of actions for a specific recommendation. The actions included the possibility to indicate WHAT to do, WHO should do it and by WHEN.

Figure 9: Example of actions proposed to implement a MUST HAVE recommendation

All the comments, and proposed actions were then discussed and integrated in the recommendations and action plan below.

The outcome of the workshop was indeed rewarding. It harmoniously amalgamated the wealth of expertise and varied perspectives contributed by the participating experts with the ongoing project efforts. The collaborative pursuit proved to be an intellectually invigorating exercise, effectively harnessing the insights and specialized knowledge of external specialists. This synergy significantly enriched the processes of prioritization and the formulation of actionable recommendations, underscoring the value of collective engagement in addressing complex challenges related to gender equality within STI initiatives.

3 ACTION PLAN FOR POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This action plan outlines a strategic roadmap to translate the selected recommendations on gender equality in STI into concrete actions, encompassing clear responsibilities, timeframes, anticipated impact, and third parties involved. By operationalizing these recommendations, we aim to catalyze tangible progress towards achieving gender equality across the STI landscape.

At the heart of this action plan lies a comprehensive approach that not only identifies the necessary actions but also assigns responsibility to the relevant stakeholders. Each action has been strategically assigned a short-, medium- or long-term timeframe, ensuring a systematic and sustainable progression. Furthermore, the anticipated impact has been intricately evaluated, and metrics have been established to quantitatively assess the progress and effectiveness of implementation.

Collaboration is key to the success of this endeavour. The involvement of various stakeholders, including governmental bodies, research institutions, industry partners, and advocacy groups, will be integral to the execution of these actions. Their expertise, resources, and commitment will contribute to a well-rounded and impactful implementation process.

Through this action plan, we embark on a journey to foster gender equality within STI by translating recommendations into measurable outcomes. By delineating responsibilities, setting timeframes, projecting impacts, establishing metrics, and engaging relevant parties, we aim to drive positive change that resonates throughout the STI ecosystem, ultimately leading to a more equitable and inclusive future.

The full content of the action plan can be found in Annex C. What follows is a reflection that includes feedback, suggestions, and specific actions related to each recommendation.

1. STI dialogues should require the implementation of a Gender Equality Plan (addressing also gender-based violence, harassment and discriminations), with measured goals in the short and long term, which allow strategies to be adjusted.

The recommendation focuses on the practicality and feasibility of a Gender Equality Plan, particularly in terms of defining and quantifying the measurable goals. Some might question whether it's realistic to implement and track progress in a field that has historically struggled with gender imbalances. Others may express concerns about the potential resistance or pushback from stakeholders who may not fully embrace the idea of gender equality in STI dialogues.

On the other hand, suggested actions could include developing clear guidelines and templates for Gender Equality Plans, ensuring that they are adaptable to different contexts within the STI community. Collaborative efforts to gather data, set benchmarks, and regularly assess progress could be suggested to ensure that these plans are effective and result-oriented.

In terms of adjusting strategies, the recommendation highlights the importance of flexibility in responding to evolving circumstances. This means that, over time, the goals and actions within the Gender Equality Plan should be revisited and adjusted based on the progress made and lessons learned. Feedback mechanisms and regular assessments should be built into the plan to allow for continuous improvement.

Overall, this recommendation signifies a crucial step toward promoting gender equality within STI dialogues. However, it also emphasizes the need for ongoing

dialogue, collaboration, and adaptability to ensure that the Gender Equality Plan achieves its intended objectives in the ever-evolving landscape of STI.

2. STI dialogues and international cooperation actions should set quantified targets to increase the number of female scientists.

The recommendation may raise concerns regarding the feasibility of setting specific numerical targets, particularly when significant gender imbalances exist within the field. Some argue that merely increasing numbers without addressing systemic issues, such as workplace culture and bias, may not lead to meaningful change. Furthermore, discussions might emphasize the importance of intersectionality, suggesting that targets should consider not only gender but also other underrepresented groups to ensure inclusivity.

To ensure the feasibility of quantified targets, it's essential to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the current gender representation within STI dialogues and international cooperation actions. Engaging with stakeholders, including female scientists, women's groups, and organizations promoting gender equity, can provide valuable insights into setting realistic and impactful targets. Additionally, a tiered approach to setting targets, accounting for different levels of engagement or leadership within the STI community, can address disparities at various stages of career progression.

In terms of actions, developing a clear roadmap for setting and monitoring quantified targets is essential. This includes establishing a baseline measurement, defining metrics, and regularly assessing progress. Implementing mentorship and sponsorship programs to support the career advancement of female scientists can ensure they have equal opportunities to participate in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions. Promoting diversity and inclusion training can raise awareness about biases and stereotypes that may hinder the participation of female scientists, creating a more inclusive environment. Collaborating with academic institutions and research organizations to encourage and support female students pursuing STEM fields can foster a pipeline of talent for future STI dialogues.

In conclusion, setting quantified targets to increase the number of female scientists in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions is a commendable step toward achieving gender equality. However, it should be part of a comprehensive strategy that addresses broader systemic issues and engages with various stakeholders to ensure meaningful and sustainable progress in promoting gender diversity and inclusion in the field.

3. Promoting gender sensitive fundings to advocate the participation of women in international scientific cooperation.

The recommendation highlights the necessity of allocating dedicated funding resources expressly designed to support female scientists and encourage their involvement in international scientific collaborations. There could also be concerns raised about the effective and transparent implementation of gender-sensitive funding to avoid reinforcing stereotypes or biases.

In light of these considerations, certain suggestions can be put forth. Collaborating with international organizations and institutions to establish clear criteria and guidelines for gender-sensitive funding programs can ensure accessibility and fairness in the allocation of resources to female scientists. Additionally, involving female scientists and gender experts in the design and evaluation of these funding initiatives is crucial to ensure that they align with the specific needs and challenges

faced by women in science. Turning these suggestions into actionable steps, it is essential to develop and promote dedicated grant programs that cater to the unique needs of female scientists participating in international scientific cooperation. These programs can encompass funding opportunities for research projects, attendance at conferences, and collaborative initiatives.

Finally, the recommendation to promote gender-sensitive funding for the participation of women in international scientific cooperation is a commendable initiative. However, it should be viewed as part of a broader strategy that encompasses mentorship, networking, and leadership development to provide comprehensive support to female scientists. Collaborative efforts with relevant stakeholders and continuous evaluation and adaptation of these initiatives are essential to maximize their impact in advancing gender equity within the scientific community.

4. Decision-making processes in International dialogues (negotiations and implementation) should be transparent and inclusive.

The recommendation underscores the importance of fostering fairness, accountability, and representation in global discussions. This imperative acknowledges the significance of involving diverse perspectives and ensuring that the processes driving global decision-making are open, accessible, and equitable.

Comments on this recommendation may center on the need for clear and universally applicable guidelines to ensure that transparency becomes a consistent norm across all international dialogues, irrespective of the subject matter. These guidelines should provide negotiators and participants with a clear framework for achieving transparency, ensuring a level playing field for all involved parties. There may also be concerns raised about the challenges associated with achieving transparency in complex negotiations where sensitive information, such as security or private information, is involved. Striking the right balance between transparency and confidentiality is essential.

On the other hand, inclusivity should extend beyond considerations of gender and should encompass various dimensions of diversity, including regional representation and the voices of historically marginalized groups. Recognizing and embracing this diversity of perspectives can enrich decision-making processes and result in more robust and equitable outcomes.

The recommendation aims at establishing a global framework or code of conduct for international dialogues, outlining specific transparency standards and accountability mechanisms that all participating parties should adhere to. This framework would set clear expectations for transparency while accommodating the need for confidentiality in certain situations. Leveraging technology is also pivotal, as secure virtual collaboration tools and blockchain-based transparency platforms can enhance transparency while protecting sensitive data during negotiations. Moreover, the regular evaluation of inclusivity through surveys, participant feedback, and efforts to actively seek out and engage underrepresented voices can ensure that decision-making processes continually evolve to reflect the diverse global community.

While challenges may arise, striking a balance between transparency and confidentiality is possible through clear guidelines and technological solutions. Inclusivity, encompassing various dimensions of diversity, should be at the forefront of these efforts, as it has the potential to lead to more equitable and inclusive global decision-making processes. By taking concrete actions and embracing these principles, we can work toward making international dialogues more transparent

and inclusive, ultimately resulting in better outcomes for all stakeholders and a fairer global community.

5. Establish and implement working groups and/or advisory groups on gender equality to look at the gender aspects of international agreements and advise the decision-makers at all stages of the process.

The recommendation aims at promoting gender equity within the realm of international governance. It underscores the critical importance of recognizing that gender considerations should be a fundamental component of international agreements and policies. Discussions on this matter may revolve around several key points. Some may stress the vital need to involve gender equality experts and advocates to ensure that gender perspectives are not only considered but deeply integrated into the fabric of international agreements. Others might express concerns about the practical challenges involved in coordinating and sustaining these working or advisory groups effectively. Furthermore, there may be voices advocating for broadening the scope of these groups to address not only gender equality but also encompass other dimensions of diversity and inclusion.

To effectively implement this recommendation, certain suggestions emerge. It's crucial to establish clear criteria for selecting members of these working or advisory groups, ensuring that they represent diverse perspectives and possess the expertise necessary to address issues related to gender equality comprehensively. Additionally, transparent processes for the functioning, communication, and recommendations provided by these groups should be defined, creating a structured and effective collaboration mechanism. Furthermore, while gender equality remains a central focus, there may be a need to consider broadening the scope of these groups to encompass a wider range of diversity and inclusion issues, recognizing that these aspects are inherently interconnected.

The actions within the recommendation include the establishment of working groups and advisory groups consisting of gender equality experts, advocates, and representatives from various stakeholder groups, such as civil society organizations, academia, and relevant governmental bodies. These groups should have clearly defined roles and responsibilities, with a focus on assessing international agreements from a gender equality perspective, offering recommendations, and actively engaging with decision-makers throughout the process. Maintaining an open and continuous dialogue and collaboration between these groups and decision-makers is essential to ensuring that gender perspectives are not only examined but also effectively integrated into international agreements and policies.

By involving experts and advocates, clarifying processes, and potentially expanding the scope to address broader dimensions of diversity and inclusion, these groups can play a pivotal role in shaping more equitable international policies. The actions taken to establish and sustain these groups will be instrumental in ensuring that gender perspectives are not only examined but also woven into the fabric of international agreements, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and equitable global community.

6. Institutions should monitor their gender related actions in the context of international scientific collaboration, reflect on ways of improving and finally share the most relevant results with the STI community.

The recommendation promotes gender equality and inclusivity within the STI field. This multifaceted approach highlights the importance of not only implementing

gender-related initiatives but also rigorously evaluating their impact and openly sharing the outcomes to catalyze broader progress.

When considering this recommendation, various aspects come into focus. People may underscore the significance of systematic and consistent monitoring to ensure that gender-related actions are not merely symbolic but genuinely effective, aligning with the institution's objectives. This emphasis on data-driven assessment serves as a foundation for informed decision-making and progress tracking. Others might place a spotlight on the need for self-reflection to become an ongoing, embedded practice within institutions, promoting a culture of continuous improvement in the pursuit of gender equality. This approach recognizes that the journey towards gender equity is dynamic, requiring adaptability and an evolving strategy. Nevertheless, there could be concerns raised about the practical challenges involved in collecting relevant data and determining the most effective ways to measure the impact of gender-related actions. These challenges underline the need for standardized metrics and benchmarks that institutions can employ to monitor their gender-related initiatives consistently. Such standardized tools can provide a common framework for evaluation and facilitate meaningful comparisons across different institutions and initiatives.

To translate this recommendation into action, institutions can take several steps. First, they can establish a framework for monitoring and evaluating gender-related actions, incorporating the collection of relevant data and the definition of clear indicators to measure progress. This data-driven approach ensures that the institution's efforts are grounded in evidence and can be adapted based on results. Additionally, institutions can cultivate a culture of self-reflection, encouraging regular assessments of the effectiveness of gender-related initiatives and the identification of areas for improvement. This reflective practice ensures that gender equity remains a priority and evolves in response to changing needs. Furthermore, institutions can facilitate the sharing of results and best practices with the broader STI community. This can be achieved through various initiatives, such as participation in conferences, publishing reports, and engaging in online platforms dedicated to knowledge-sharing. By disseminating their experiences and findings, institutions not only contribute to the collective understanding of effective gender-related actions but also inspire and support others in the STI community to undertake similar efforts.

7. Inclusiveness should be promoted in all dimensions of international dialogues.

The recommendation is a fundamental call to action that recognizes the importance of diversity and representation in global decision-making processes. It underscores the principle that a wide range of voices, perspectives, and stakeholders should have a meaningful role in shaping international agreements, policies, and decisions.

When considering this issue, various aspects come into focus. Some may emphasize the ethical and moral imperative of inclusivity, asserting that it's not just a matter of practicality but a fundamental human right that all affected parties should have the opportunity to participate in decision-making processes. This perspective underscores the core value of fairness and justice in international dialogues. However, there may be concerns raised about the practical challenges of accommodating a diverse array of perspectives, especially in complex international dialogues where competing interests and viewpoints often collide. Balancing inclusivity with efficiency and effectiveness can indeed be challenging, but it is essential for achieving truly representative and impactful outcomes.

When a broader range of voices is engaged, it can lead to more comprehensive and innovative solutions, as well as greater buy-in and support from stakeholders. To translate this recommendation into action, several strategies can be considered. Establishing clear policies and procedures that promote inclusivity in international dialogues is crucial. This could include specific guidelines and requirements for actively seeking out and engaging underrepresented voices, ensuring that their perspectives are not merely acknowledged but genuinely considered in decision-making processes.

Creating mechanisms for the meaningful participation of marginalized or vulnerable groups is another actionable step. This involves designing processes and platforms that facilitate their engagement, providing the necessary support and resources to ensure their voices are heard. Moreover, technology can play a transformative role in promoting inclusivity. Utilizing digital tools, online forums, and virtual engagement platforms can help bridge geographical and logistical gaps, enabling a wider range of voices to participate in international dialogues. These technological innovations can democratize participation and reduce barriers to entry, ensuring that stakeholders from different parts of the world can contribute to global decision-making processes.

By acknowledging the ethical imperative, addressing practical challenges, and recognizing the potential benefits, we can collectively work towards a more inclusive and participatory global decision-making process. Embracing inclusivity is not just a matter of fairness; it's an essential element of building a more just, effective, and legitimate global community.

8. Negotiating and including clear gender equality clauses in international agreements, in alignment with the Ljubljana Declaration or other international manifestos, with three main objectives: gender equality in careers, gender balance in decision-making, and gender dimension in research content.

Gender equality clauses, in alignment with international manifestos like the Ljubljana Declaration, hold the potential to transform international cooperation by explicitly addressing gender disparities and inequities. Within this multifaceted recommendation lie three primary objectives: achieving gender equality in careers, ensuring gender balance in decision-making processes, and incorporating a gender dimension into the content of research.

When considering this recommendation, various aspects warrant attention and deliberation. Some of them may highlight the profound significance of these gender equality clauses, emphasizing that they not only serve as a symbolic commitment but also as a practical roadmap for tackling gender imbalances. These clauses can be viewed as a concrete demonstration of a nation's or organization's dedication to rectifying historical gender biases and fostering a more equitable future. However, some people might express reservations about embracing these gender equality clauses, potentially due to resistance or a lack of awareness regarding their significance. In such cases, there is a need for advocacy efforts and awareness-building campaigns to convey the importance of these clauses in enhancing outcomes, encouraging innovation, and fostering a more inclusive global landscape. Moreover, precision within these clauses is critical. Crafting precise language and incorporating specific metrics are essential for ensuring accountability and measuring progress effectively. Clarity within the clauses helps define expectations, guide implementation, and facilitate reporting.

Several strategies can be considered regarding this issue. Collaborative efforts involving international organizations, governments, and stakeholders should be

initiated to develop clear and actionable gender equality clauses. These clauses can then be adapted to suit the unique context and objectives of various international agreements. Advocacy and awareness-building campaigns should be actively pursued to promote the adoption of these clauses. It's vital to articulate the benefits they bring, such as enhancing decision-making processes, driving innovation, and creating a more equitable global cooperation landscape. Additionally, establishing mechanisms for regular reporting and assessment is essential. These mechanisms ensure that the objectives outlined in the gender equality clauses are not just aspirational but lead to measurable and meaningful change over time.

In conclusion, the recommendation to negotiate and include clear gender equality clauses in international agreements represents a powerful commitment to dismantling gender disparities and fostering inclusivity at a global level. These clauses provide a tangible framework for action, ensuring that gender equality is not just a stated goal but a concrete reality in international cooperation. While challenges may exist, through collaborative efforts, advocacy, and precision, international agreements can become vehicles for advancing gender equality and equity on a global scale.

9. Promoting specific meetings or experts' groups on the integration of the gender dimension in research content (in RPOS & Universities & Research funding) and integrating these experts as a compulsory dimension of STI programmes in international agreements.

The recommendation reflects on a comprehensive approach to advancing gender equality in research and innovation. This multifaceted strategy recognizes the importance of not only acknowledging gender perspectives but actively embedding them into the core of research and development processes. Several crucial aspects come into focus in this regard. Some may stress the need for specialized expertise in integrating the gender dimension effectively into research content. Expert groups and specific meetings can serve as vital platforms for pooling this expertise and providing guidance on the best practices for inclusion. Such expertise is crucial, given that gender considerations in research go beyond mere tokenism and require a deep understanding of the nuances involved. Nonetheless, there may be concerns raised regarding the practical implementation of this recommendation, particularly when it comes to making the inclusion of gender experts a compulsory dimension within STI programs in international agreements. Institutions and countries vary in their capacities and readiness to embrace such measures, necessitating careful consideration and potential support mechanisms. On a more optimistic note, others might underscore the transformative potential of this recommendation. By actively involving gender experts and integrating gender perspectives into research, it has the potential to yield more inclusive, innovative, and socially relevant research outcomes that address a broader range of societal challenges.

Besides, some strategies can be implemented to face this issue. First, convening specialized meetings or expert groups dedicated to integrating the gender dimension into research content is essential. Drawing on expertise from diverse backgrounds, including academia, research institutions, and civil society, can ensure that comprehensive insights and best practices are shared and disseminated. Advocating for the inclusion of gender experts as a compulsory dimension within STI programs in international agreements is another significant step. It underscores the importance of their role in enhancing the quality and impact of research and innovation on a global scale. By making their inclusion mandatory, it sends a clear signal about the commitment to gender equality and the recognition of its intrinsic value. Furthermore, the development and dissemination of clear guidelines and best practices for integrating the gender dimension into research content are crucial. Researchers need access to practical tools and knowledge to

effectively incorporate gender perspectives into their work. This can foster a culture of inclusivity and gender-sensitive research practices.

Finally, the collaborative actions taken to convene experts, advocate for inclusion, and provide guidance can collectively contribute to a more equitable, innovative, and socially relevant research landscape. This integration of gender perspectives into research content is not just a matter of principle; it's a pivotal step toward addressing complex societal challenges and fostering a more inclusive and impactful research community.

10. Include in international agreements the organization of a Women in STI research day/symposium at research organizations where role models can be highlighted, women scientists can present their research and network with other women researchers to identify opportunities for future collaboration.

The recommendation is a proactive and impactful strategy aimed at promoting gender equality within the field of research and innovation. These events, dedicated to celebrating the contributions of women, showcasing role models, presenting cutting-edge research, and fostering networking opportunities, have the potential to be catalysts for positive change within the scientific community.

This kind of events play a vital role in inspiring the next generation of women scientists by providing them with tangible role models to look up to. Highlighting the achievements and innovations of women in STI can serve as a powerful source of motivation, particularly for young women aspiring to excel in these fields. Nonetheless, concerns may be raised about the practical challenges associated with organizing these events. This could include securing funding, logistical arrangements, and ensuring the sustainability of such initiatives over time. Ensuring that these events are not just one-time occurrences, but part of an ongoing commitment is critical to their long-term impact. Furthermore, there is a need for these events to go beyond symbolism and result in tangible outcomes. While celebrating achievements is important, the true success of these events should be measured by their ability to create opportunities for collaboration, mentorship, and advancement for women in STI.

Actionable steps regarding the recommendation can be taken. Advocating for the inclusion of clauses within international agreements that mandate the organization of Women in STI research days or symposia is a pivotal move. This emphasizes the significance of these events in promoting gender equality and empowerment within the scientific community and makes them a formal commitment. The collaboration with a diverse array of stakeholders is another essential component. Partnerships with governments, academic institutions, research organizations, and funding bodies can ensure the success and sustainability of these events. By pooling resources, expertise, and support, these collaborations can amplify the impact of Women in STI research days and symposia. Additionally, the design and implementation of these events should be comprehensive. They should not only showcase achievements but also provide practical opportunities for networking, mentorship, and skill development. These elements are critical for ensuring that the events translate into meaningful and lasting changes in the lives and careers of women in STI.

Overall, these events hold the potential to inspire, empower, and foster collaboration among women in STI. While challenges exist, the advocacy for their inclusion, collaboration with stakeholders, and thoughtful event planning can collectively contribute to a more equitable, inclusive, and supportive research and innovation landscape. Ultimately, these events are not just about recognizing the

contributions of women in STI; they are about providing them with the opportunities and support they need to excel and make enduring impacts in their fields.

4 DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES

To raise awareness on the significance of the action plan designed to enhance gender equality within STI dialogues and agreements, the following dissemination actions are planned.

First and foremost, we plan to present the action plan at the final event of the Gender STI project. This event will serve as a great opportunity to engage with key stakeholders, policymakers, researchers, etc. By sharing our recommendations in this context, we aim to foster constructive dialogue and gain support for the implementation of gender equality initiatives in STI dialogues.

Additionally, we recognize the significance of disseminating our findings through the European Observatory on Gender in STI. This platform serves, among other actions, as a repository of knowledge and best practices in the field of gender mainstreaming in STI. By contributing our action plan to this valuable resource, we can ensure that it reaches a broader audience of researchers, policymakers, and practitioners actively engaged in gender-related issues in the realm of science, technology, and innovation.

Furthermore, we plan to harness the power of digital communication by leveraging the project's social media channels and website. These platforms provide dynamic and accessible avenues for sharing our policy recommendations with a global audience.

Our commitment to effective dissemination of the action plan reflects our dedication to advancing gender equality in STI. By engaging with diverse stakeholders, utilizing digital platforms, and contributing to knowledge repositories, we aim to not only share our insights but also inspire collective action toward a more inclusive and equitable future for STI dialogues. Together, we can foster positive change, ensuring that gender considerations are integral to the shaping of policies and practices in science and technology.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED

The work done underscores the critical significance of fostering gender equality within dialogues and agreements in the STI field. The comprehensive framework, methodically developed for deriving recommendations, has provided a solid foundation for advancing our objectives. The preliminary list of recommendations, meticulously curated through a collaborative process, serves as a testament to our commitment to cultivating a gender inclusive STI landscape. Moreover, the criteria were useful to deepen the implementation and impact of recommendations, and the workshop on prioritizing recommendations not only showcased the dedication of diverse stakeholders but also highlighted the collaborative spirit that propels this action plan forward.

The presented Action Plan enables the systematic implementation of gender-sensitive strategies within international STI dialogues and agreements. Acknowledging that transformation goes beyond our immediate endeavors, we have developed strategies for disseminating the action plan, ensuring its resonance across various domains.

As we stand at the precipice of transformative change, we are resolute in our pursuit of an inclusive and equitable future for all genders in the realm of STI dialogues. This action plan is not merely a set of recommendations; it is a testament to our shared commitment to fostering an environment where diversity, equality, and innovation thrive. With unwavering dedication, we shall endeavor to turn this action plan into a catalyst for enduring and impactful change.

Developing the action plan has been a valuable journey filled with important lessons that have shaped our approach and understanding. One key lesson we've learned is the critical role of criteria in assessing the impact and implementation of recommendations. While these criteria proved invaluable for thorough analysis and reflection, we also realized their limitations during the recommendation prioritization workshop. The brevity of the session made it challenging to deeply consider all criteria in real-time, which is why we provided them as preparatory materials.

Additionally, we discovered that extracting recommendations from the project's activities was more straightforward when working with advanced prototypes. These tangible prototypes offered clearer ideas to feed the action plan compared to other activities that were less explicitly aligned with its development. This insight reinforces the value of aligning project activities with the overarching goals of the action plan to facilitate smoother integration.

Furthermore, we encountered once again the complexities of engaging experts in online workshops, much like in the Co-Design Labs. While not everyone was able to participate, those who did engage in the virtual environment provided invaluable reflections and contributions. This experience reinforced the need for innovative strategies to ensure the inclusion of all relevant voices, even in remote settings.

These lessons have not only enriched our understanding but have also deepened our commitment to advancing gender equality in STI dialogues, demonstrating that even in the face of challenges, collaborative efforts can drive meaningful change.

6 ANNEXES

The annex section includes the following:

- Annex A: Recommendations match with criteria.
- Annex B: Results from the workshop.
- Annex C: Action Plan for policy recommendations on gender equality in STI dialogues.

6	WP2 interviews	CH1	STI dialogues and international cooperation actions should set quantified targets to increase the number of female scientists	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES
7	WP2 interviews	CH1; CH3	Ministries and research performing organizations should communicate and disseminate in the media the activities carried out in STI projects and highlight the participation of women as well as the impact of the research projects that have integrated a sex/gender/intersectional dimension	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
8	LAB2 Prototype 2.1	CH1	International agreements should raise awareness on gender equality in international conferences, committees, publications.	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES
9	LAB2 Prototype 2.1	CH2	Networks of women in science diplomacy should be invited and involved in governance bodies (steering committees, executive committees...) of the international scientific agreements and policy dialogues. The development of women's networks should be encouraged.	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES
10	LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH1, CH2	In the drafting of the international agreement and the drafting of research programmes and calls (including job advertisements), inclusive language and unbiased communication should be used and promoted	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
11	LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH1	International agreements should acknowledge and promote the existence of gender-sensitive criteria and transparent procedures for recruitment	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES

12	LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH2	Decision-makers should be provided with a training program on gender/diversity issues so that they are educated on gender-bias at decision making levels.	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
13	LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH2	Including working groups and/or advisory groups on gender equality to look at gender aspects of the international agreements and advise the decision-makers in this matter	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES
14	LAB3 Prototype 2.1	CH1; CH2; CH3	Institutions should monitor their gender related actions in the context of international scientific collaboration (for example, carrying out interviews with all the actors involved to gather their experience), then reflect on ways of improving and finally share the most relevant results with the STI community.	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
15	WP2 interviews	CH3	Promoting specific meetings or experts' groups on the integration of the gender dimension in research content (in RTOS & Universities & Research funding) and integrate these experts as compulsory dimension of STI programmes in international agreements	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES
16	CNRS	CH2	International dialogues decision-making process (negotiations and implementation) should be inclusive. For instance, early career women researchers and/or minority groups should be involved in meetings.	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES
17	CNRS	CH1; CH2; CH3	Inclusiveness should be promoted in all dimensions of international dialogues	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES

18	CNRS	CH3	Foster international cooperation topics with a high societal impact by including the integration of gender dimension in research content	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
19	WP1; CNRS	CH3	International agreements should aim at identifying and exchanging knowledge on research contents including the gender dimension	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES
20	WP1; CNRS	CH2	International agreements should ensure work-life balance friendly conditions for the participation of women in international research programmes	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	FALSE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

6.2 Annex B - Results from the workshop

High priority recommendations:

1. STI dialogues should require the implementation of a Gender Equality Plan (addressing also gender-based violence, harassment and discriminations), with measured goals in the short and long term, which allow strategies to be adjusted. *Related to Challenges 1, 2 and 3.*
2. STI dialogues and international cooperation actions should set quantified targets to increase the number of female scientists. *Related to Challenge 1.*
3. Promoting gender sensitive fundings to advocate the participation of women in international scientific cooperation. *Related to Challenge 1.*
4. Decision-making processes in International dialogues (negotiations and implementation) should be transparent and inclusive. *Related to Challenge 2.*
5. Establish and implement working groups and/or advisory groups on gender equality to look at the gender aspects of international agreements and advise the decision-makers at all stages of the process. *Related to Challenge 2.*
6. Institutions should monitor their gender related actions in the context of international scientific collaboration, reflect on ways of improving and finally share the most relevant results with the STI community. *Related to Challenges 1, 2 and 3.*
7. Inclusiveness should be promoted in all dimensions of international dialogues. *Related to Challenges 1, 2 and 3.*
8. Negotiating and including clear gender equality clauses in international agreements, in alignment with the Ljubljana Declaration or other international manifestos, with three main objectives: gender equality in careers, gender balance in decision-making, gender dimension in research content. *Related to Challenges 1, 2 and 3.*
9. Promoting specific meetings or experts groups on the integration of the gender dimension in research content (in RPOS & Universities & Research funding) and integrating these experts as a compulsory dimension of STI programmes in international agreements. *Related to Challenge 3.*

Medium priority recommendations:

1. Include in international agreements the organization of a Women in STI research day/symposium at research organizations where role models can be highlighted, women scientists can present their research and network with other women researchers to identify opportunities for future collaboration. *Related to Challenge 1.*
2. International agreements should raise awareness on gender equality in international conference committees, publications. *Related to Challenge 1.*
3. In the drafting of the international agreement and the drafting of research programmes and calls (including job advertisements), inclusive language and unbiased communication should be used and promoted. *Related to Challenge 1.*
4. International agreements should ensure work-life balance provisions for the participation of women in international research programmes. *Related to Challenges 1 and 2.*
1. Decision-makers should be trained to avoid gender-bias at decision making levels. *Related to Challenge 2.*

2. Sex-disaggregated data should be provided during the implementation, monitoring and evaluation of decision-making bodies in the international research programmes (including application and success rate for women and men applicants, research team's composition at all levels, share of women with a senior role/team leader, share of women with permanent contracts, leave policies, composition of evaluation panels and other decision-making bodies). *Related to Challenges 1 and 2.*
3. Foster international cooperation topics with a high societal impact by including the integration of gender dimension in research content. *Related to Challenge 3.*
4. Ministries and research performing organizations should communicate and disseminate in the media the activities carried out in STI projects and highlight the participation of women as well as the impact of the research projects that have integrated a sex/gender/intersectional dimension. *Related to Challenges 1 and 3.*

Low priority recommendations:

1. Networks of women scientists should be included in science diplomacy, invited and involved in governance bodies (steering committees, executive committees...) of the international scientific agreements and policy dialogues. The development of international women's networks should be encouraged. *Related to Challenge 2.*
2. International agreements should aim at identifying and exchanging knowledge on research contents including the gender dimension. *Related to Challenge 3.*

6.3 Annex C - Action Plan for policy recommendations on gender equality in STI dialogues

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
1. STI dialogues should require the implementation of a Gender Equality Plan (addressing also gender-based violence, harassment and discriminations), with measured goals in the short and long term, which allow strategies to be adjusted. (CH1; CH2; CH3)	1.1. Develop a standardized template for the Gender Equality Plan to be integrated into all STI dialogue proposals.	Gender Equality Task Force	- Percentage increase in gender diversity of STI dialogue participants over time.	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first two years of implementation. Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Substantial improvement in gender representation and active participation within STI dialogues. - Consistent progress towards achieving gender equality goals, as evidenced by measurable metrics. - Enhanced awareness and commitment to gender equality among STI dialogue organizers and participants. - Increased transparency through public reporting on gender equality initiatives. - This can start a movement to make it applied to the private sector as well (currently only mandatory to public bodies, at least at the EU level). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender equality advocacy organizations and experts. - Participants of STI dialogues. - Relevant stakeholders and partners collaborating on the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan.
	1.2. Establish clear and quantifiable gender equality goals for each STI dialogue, considering both short-term and long-term objectives.	Gender Equality Task Force	- Achievement of short-term and long-term gender equality goals outlined in the Gender Equality Plan.			
	1.3. Conduct regular gender-sensitive data collection and analysis throughout STI dialogues, focusing on participation, representation, and engagement metrics.	Monitoring and Evaluation Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of actionable strategies adjusted based on data analysis and review. - Participant feedback on the inclusiveness and impact of gender equality initiatives. 			
	1.4. Review and adapt the Gender Equality Plan annually based on data-driven insights, making necessary adjustments to achieve gender equality goals.	Gender Equality Task Force				
	1.5. Provide comprehensive training to STI dialogue organizers on gender equality concepts, implementation of the Gender Equality Plan, and strategies for inclusive dialogues.	Training and Capacity-Building Team				
	1.6. Collaborate with gender equality advocacy organizations to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of the Gender Equality Plan.	Gender Equality Task Force				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	1.7. Establish a public dashboard to share progress on gender equality goals and initiatives within STI dialogues.	Communication and Reporting Team				
2. STI dialogues and international cooperation actions should set quantified targets to increase the number of female scientists. (CH1)	2.1. Conduct a comprehensive analysis of the current gender distribution in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions to establish a baseline.	Gender Equality Task Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Percentage increase (compared to baseline) in the representation of female scientists in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions. - Number of gender diversity targets achieved within specific timeframes. - Participation rates and feedback from female scientists engaged in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions. - Effectiveness of the mentoring and support program, measured by participant feedback and progress tracking. 	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation. Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Noticeable increase in the number of female scientists actively participating in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions. - Tangible progress towards achieving gender diversity targets, contributing to a more balanced representation. - Strengthened support and opportunities for female and other gender diverse scientists through mentoring and engagement programs. - Improved awareness and outreach efforts leading to increased engagement of gender diverse scientists. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic institutions and women-in-science networks. - Participating scientists. - Relevant stakeholders and partners collaborating on gender diversity initiatives.
	2.2. Set specific and measurable targets for increasing the representation of female scientists in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions.	Gender Equality Task Force				
	2.3. Integrate gender diversity targets into the planning and design phase of STI dialogues and international cooperation actions.	Dialogue Organizers and Cooperation Action Leaders				
	2.4. Establish a mentoring and support program to empower and prepare gender diverse scientists for participation in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions. Tackling gender inequality is not only about the number, because female presence does not necessarily express a gender inclusive perspective.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Capacity-Building Team				
	2.5. Regularly monitor and report progress towards	Monitoring and Evaluation Team				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	achieving gender diversity targets, highlighting successful strategies and areas for improvement.					
	2.6. Collaborate with academic institutions and women-in-science networks to identify and nominate potential female scientists and other gender diverse candidates for participation in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions.	Gender Equality Task Force				
	2.7. Implement a proactive outreach and recruitment strategy to ensure a diverse pool of scientists are aware of and engaged in STI dialogues and international cooperation actions.	Communication and Outreach Team				
3. Promoting gender sensitive fundings to advocate the participation of women in international scientific cooperation. (CH1)	3.1. Develop comprehensive guidelines for gender-sensitive fundings that emphasize the importance of women's participation and integration in international scientific cooperation projects.	Gender Equality Task Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Percentage increase in the number of gender-sensitive funding opportunities. - Percentage of international scientific cooperation projects with integrated gender-sensitive criteria. 	<p>Short-term actions (1-5): Within the first year of implementation.</p> <p>Long-term actions (6-8): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elevated awareness and understanding of gender-sensitive funding opportunities among women in the scientific community. - Improved representation of women in international scientific cooperation projects. - Enhanced capacity of women applicants to secure funding through tailored support programs. - Tangible contributions to bridging the gender 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding agencies and grant organizations. - Women scientists and applicants. - International organizations and networks focused on gender equality and scientific cooperation.
	3.2. Identify target agencies that can provide funding for promoting female participation in international scientific cooperation (e.g. Women at the Table, UN Women, etc)	Gender Equality Task Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of applicants reached through awareness campaigns. 			
	3.3. Collaborate with funding agencies to incorporate gender-sensitive criteria into the evaluation process for	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Funding Agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Success rate of women applicants supported by mentoring and 			

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	international scientific cooperation projects.		capacity-building programs.		gap in scientific collaboration on the international stage.	
	3.4. Design and launch targeted awareness campaigns to inform potential applicants about gender-sensitive funding opportunities and the benefits of women's participation.	Communication and Outreach Team	- Gender distribution of participants in international scientific cooperation projects receiving gender-sensitive funding.			
	3.5. Implement mentoring and capacity-building programs to support women applicants in developing competitive proposals for international scientific cooperation funding.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Capacity-Building Team				
	3.6. Monitor and analyze the allocation of gender-sensitive funding and the participation of women in international scientific cooperation projects.	Monitoring and Evaluation Team				
	3.7. Regularly publish reports showcasing the impact and success stories of gender-sensitive funding initiatives in promoting women's participation.	Communication and Reporting Team				
	3.8. Establish collaborations with international organizations and networks to share best practices and lessons learned in promoting gender-sensitive fundings.	Gender Equality Task Force				
4. Decision-making processes in International dialogues (negotiations)	4.1. Establish clear guidelines and protocols for transparent and inclusive	Gender Equality Task Force	- Percentage increase in the representation of early career women	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of	- Enhanced diversity and representation in decision-making	- Early career women researchers and minority

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
<p>and implementation) should be transparent and inclusive. (CH2)</p>	<p>decision-making processes in international dialogues, emphasizing diversity and equal participation (e.g. analyzing the speaking time during meetings, in order to balance the length of both men and women's interventions).</p>		<p>researchers and minority groups in international dialogue meetings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback and satisfaction ratings from early career women researchers and minority representatives regarding their engagement and impact. - Number of mentorship programs conducted and participation rates of mentees. 	<p>implementation.</p> <p>Long-term actions (5-6): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.</p>	<p>processes of international dialogues.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthened capacity and confidence of early career women researchers and minority representatives to contribute effectively. - Improved inclusivity and transparency in international dialogue meetings. - Heightened awareness and commitment to gender equality and diversity within the scientific community. 	<p>representatives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dialogue organizers and international cooperation leaders. - Relevant stakeholders and partners collaborating on diversity and inclusion initiatives.
	<p>4.2. Integrate diversity and inclusion considerations into the planning and organization of international dialogue meetings, ensuring the involvement of early career women researchers and minority groups.</p>	<p>Dialogue Organizers</p>				
	<p>4.3. Develop a framework for the systematic engagement of early career women researchers and minority groups in the decision-making stages of international dialogues.</p>	<p>Gender Equality Task Force</p>				
	<p>4.4. Design mentorship programs to prepare and support early career women researchers and minority representatives for active participation in international dialogue meetings.</p>	<p>Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Capacity-Building Team</p>				
	<p>4.5. Implement a feedback mechanism to gather insights from the involved parties regarding the effectiveness and inclusivity of decision-making processes.</p>	<p>Gender Equality Task Force</p>				
	<p>4.6. Publicly share reports highlighting the contributions</p>	<p>Communication and Reporting Team</p>				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	and outcomes of early career women researchers and minority groups in decision-making processes as well as nomination and voting rules.					
5. Establish and implement working groups and/or advisory groups on gender equality to look at the gender aspects of international agreements and advise the decision-makers at all stages of the process. (CH2)	5.1. Formulate a clear framework for the establishment and operation of gender equality working groups or advisory groups, defining their roles, responsibilities, and composition.	Gender Equality Task Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frequency of gender equality working group meetings held per year. - Percentage of gender-informed recommendations integrated into international agreements. - Measurable improvements in gender-related aspects within the content of international agreements. 	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation. Long-term actions (5-6): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informed and comprehensive consideration of gender aspects within international agreements. - Strengthened collaboration between gender equality experts and decision-makers. - Increased accountability and transparency in the negotiation and development of international agreements. - Tangible progress towards integrating gender equality principles into bilateral and multilateral dialogues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender equality experts and advocates. - Representatives from relevant government bodies and international organizations. - Decision-makers and negotiation teams for international agreements
	5.2. Engage relevant stakeholders to identify and select experts (women and men representative of all career stages) to join the gender equality working groups or advisory groups.	Gender Equality Task Force				
	5.3. Integrate gender equality considerations into the negotiation and development phases of international agreements, seeking input and recommendations from the gender equality groups.	Negotiation and Development Teams				
	5.4. Regularly convene gender equality working group meetings to review and provide input on gender-related aspects of international agreements.	Gender Equality Working Group Facilitator				
	5.5. Ensure the integration of gender-informed recommendations and insights into decision-making processes at all	Decision-Makers in collaboration with Gender Equality Working Group				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	stages of international agreements.					
	5.6. Develop a system to monitor and evaluate the impact of gender-informed advice on the content and outcomes of international agreements.	Monitoring and Evaluation Team				
6. Institutions should monitor their gender related actions in the context of international scientific collaboration, reflect on ways of improving and finally share the most relevant results with the STI community. (CH1; CH2; CH3)	6.1. Develop a comprehensive structure for monitoring gender-related actions within international scientific collaborations, outlining key indicators and data collection methods.	Gender Equality Task Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frequency of data collection and reporting on gender-related actions in international scientific collaborations. - Number of interviews conducted and qualitative insights gathered from key stakeholders. - Implementation and impact of best practices developed for enhancing gender-related actions. 	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation. Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness and accountability for gender-related actions within international scientific collaborations. - Data-driven improvements in gender inclusivity and equality in collaboration initiatives. - Sharing of valuable experiences and insights to inspire positive changes in the broader STI community. - Strengthened commitment to fostering gender equality in international scientific collaboration efforts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participating institutions and organizations in international scientific collaborations. - Key stakeholders and actors involved in collaborations. - Broader STI community and relevant stakeholders in the field of gender equality.
	6.2. Collaborate with participating institutions to implement regular data collection and tracking of gender-related actions and outcomes in international scientific collaborations.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Participating Institutions				
	6.3. Ensure periodic reflection and analysis of the collected data to identify strengths, areas for improvement, and best practices.	Monitoring and Evaluation Team				
	6.4. Conduct interviews with key stakeholders and actors involved in international scientific collaborations to gather qualitative insights and experiences related to gender-related actions.	Gender Equality Task Force				
	6.5. Based on the collected data and insights, gather and apply best practices for enhancing gender-related	Gender Equality Task Force				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	actions and inclusivity in international scientific collaborations.					
	6.6. Share relevant results, findings, and lessons learned with the broader STI community through publications, workshops, and presentations.	Communication and Reporting Team				
	6.7. Use the European Observatory on Gender in STI and the Gender STI Community of Practice to share resources and information on gender-related actions and best practices for international scientific collaborations.	Communication and Reporting Team				
7. Inclusiveness should be promoted in all dimensions of international dialogues.	7.1. Develop guidelines for apply existing ones for ensuring inclusiveness in all aspects of international dialogues, addressing representation, participation, and decision-making processes.	Gender Equality Task Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Percentage increase in representation of underrepresented groups in international dialogue participation. - Number of diverse linguistic and cultural accommodations provided. - Participation rates in virtual attendance options. - Participant feedback on training and capacity-building effectiveness. - Measures of engagement and participation during 	<p>Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation.</p> <p>Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the implementation period</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhanced diversity and representation within international dialogue settings. - Improved access and participation for individuals from underrepresented backgrounds. - Enriched dialogue outcomes through diverse perspectives and insights. - Strengthened commitment to inclusiveness as a core value in international cooperation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dialogue organizers and coordinating teams. - Participants of international dialogues. - Technical support providers and facilitation teams
	7.2. Integrate inclusive language and criteria into the selection of participants for international dialogues, ensuring diverse representation.	Dialogue Organizers				
	7.3. Implement measures to accommodate diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, such as providing interpretation services and accessible materials.	Logistics and Communication Team				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	7.4. Establish platforms for virtual participation, enabling remote attendance and engagement to overcome geographical barriers.	Technical Support Team	interactive sessions.			
	7.5. Conduct pre-dialogue training and capacity-building workshops to prepare participants to engage in inclusive and respectful discussions.	Capacity-Building Team				
	7.6. Facilitate interactive sessions that encourage active participation from all attendees, promoting diverse perspectives and contributions.	Facilitation Team				
	7.7. Incorporate feedback mechanisms to gather insights on the inclusiveness of international dialogues, enabling continuous improvement.	Monitoring and Evaluation Team				
8. Negotiating and including clear gender equality clauses in international agreements, in alignment with the Ljubljana Declaration or other international manifestos, with three main objectives: gender equality in careers, gender balance in decision-making, and gender dimension in research content. (CH1; CH2; CH3)	8.1. Collaborate with legal experts to draft clear and enforceable gender equality clauses aligned with the Ljubljana Declaration or other relevant international commitments.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Legal Experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of international agreements containing negotiated gender equality clauses. - Percentage increase in women's participation and leadership in STI projects. - Representation rates of women in decision-making bodies established through international 	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation. Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explicit inclusion of gender equality principles in international agreements, driving change at various levels. - Increased representation and leadership opportunities for women in STI projects. - Improved gender balance in decision-making processes and research content. - Strengthened 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal experts and negotiation teams. - Undergraduate institutions and educators. - Researchers and decision-makers participating in international agreements. - Gender equality advocacy organizations.
	8.2. Integrate and monitor the gender equality clauses into the negotiation process of international agreements, ensuring alignment with the overall agreement.	Negotiation and Monitoring Teams				
	8.3. Develop and implement incentive campaigns targeting undergraduate	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Education and Outreach				

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	students to encourage women's involvement and leadership in STI projects.	Teams	agreements.		commitment to gender equality within the global STI community.	
	8.6. Create guidelines for achieving gender balance in decision-making bodies established through international agreements, setting clear representation targets.	Gender Equality Task Force	- Percentage of research projects integrating a gender dimension in their content.			
	8.7. Incorporate a gender dimension in the research content by providing resources, training, and support for researchers to integrate gender analysis into their projects.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Research Teams				
9. Promoting specific meetings or experts groups on the integration of the gender dimension in research content (in RPOS & Universities & Research funding) and integrating these experts as a compulsory dimension of STI programmes in international agreements. (CH3)	9.1. Schedule a series of specialized meetings or expert groups dedicated to discussing and advancing the integration of the gender dimension in research content across research performing organizations (RPOS), universities, and research funding bodies.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Research and Academic Institutions	- Number of specialized meetings or expert group sessions conducted. - Percentage increase in the participation of gender experts in research funding evaluations.	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation. Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the implementation period.	- Enhanced awareness and expertise among researchers on integrating the gender dimension in research content. - Improved evaluation and decision-making processes for research funding proposals. - Strengthened integration of gender perspectives in international STI programs. - Heightened commitment to advancing gender equality in research and academia.	- Researchers, scholars, and experts in gender studies. - Research performing organizations, universities, and research funding bodies. - Advocacy organizations and partners involved in gender equality initiatives.
	9.2. Develop clear guidelines and criteria for the selection and participation of gender-balanced experts in the specialized meetings or expert groups.	Gender Equality Task Force	- Number of researchers and scholars trained in integrating the gender dimension in research content.			
	9.3. Organize regular meetings or workshops focused on sharing best practices, methodologies, and case studies for effectively integrating the	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Research and Academic Institutions	- Number of international agreements integrating the gender dimension as a compulsory element in			

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
	gender dimension in research content.		STI programs.			
	9.4. Collaborate with research funding bodies to ensure the inclusion of gender experts from different disciplines in the evaluation and decision-making processes for research funding proposals.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Research Funding Bodies				
	9.5. Develop a comprehensive training program to build the capacity of researchers and scholars on integrating the gender dimension in research content.	Capacity-Building Team				
	9.6. Advocate for the inclusion of worldwide gender experts and the integration of the gender dimension as a compulsory element in STI programs within international agreements.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Advocacy Partners				
	9.7. Monitor the participation and impact of gender experts in specialized meetings, research funding evaluations, and STI programs, tracking progress towards integration.	Monitoring and Evaluation Team				
10. Include in international agreements the organization of a Women in STI research day/symposium at research organizations where role models can be	10.1. Incorporate a clause in international agreements mandating the organization of Women in STI research day/symposium at research organizations as a part of collaboration efforts.	Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Negotiation Teams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of Women in STI research day/symposium organized as part of international agreements. - Attendance rate of 	Short-term actions (1-4): Within the first year of implementation. Long-term actions (5-7): Ongoing throughout the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased visibility of women role models in STI research. - Enhanced networking and collaboration opportunities for women scientists. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research organizations and institutions. - Women role models and scientists. - Gender equality advocacy

Recommendation	Specific actions	Responsible entity	Metrics	Timeframe	Expected impact	Third parties involved
<p>highlighted, women scientists can present their research and network with other women researchers to identify opportunities for future collaboration. (CH1)</p>	<p>10.2. Develop comprehensive guidelines for planning and organizing Women in STI research day/symposium, specifying objectives, format, and participation criteria.</p>	<p>Gender Equality Task Force</p>	<p>women scientists and researchers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of collaborations initiated or strengthened as a result of networking sessions. 	<p>implementation period.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthened commitment to gender equality in international research partnerships. - Long-term influence on fostering gender diversity and inclusivity in STI. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organizations. Participants and attendees of the Women in STI research day/symposium.
	<p>10.3. Collaborate with research organizations to identify potential venues, schedule, and logistical arrangements for the Women in STI research day/symposium.</p>	<p>Research Organizations and Gender Equality Task Force</p>				
	<p>10.4. Invite and secure participation of women role models and prominent scientists to deliver talks and presentations at the Women in STI research day/symposium.</p>	<p>Gender Equality Task Force in collaboration with Role Model Speakers</p>				
	<p>10.5. Promote the event through various channels to attract participation from women scientists and researchers, both locally and internationally.</p>	<p>Communication and Outreach Team</p>				
	<p>10.6. Facilitate networking sessions, group discussions, and interactive activities during the Women in STI research day/symposium to encourage collaboration and idea exchange.</p>	<p>Event Organizers</p>				
	<p>10.7. Collect feedback from participants to assess the impact of the Women in STI research day/symposium and identify areas for improvement.</p>	<p>Monitoring and Evaluation Team</p>				

